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Unwinding – Why and How

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Central banks have lengthened their balance sheets as a result of large scale asset purchases. I first briefly describe how monetary policy is implemented, then explain why keeping large central banks' balance sheets has not delivered the expected benefits that had been advocated. I finally outline an approach to restore lean central banks' balance sheets without destabilising financial markets.

JEL Codes: E52, E58

Keywords: asset purchases, central bank, financial stability, monetary policy, unwinding

Par suite de leurs achats massifs d'actifs, les banques centrales ont accru leurs bilans. Je décris d'abord brièvement comment la politique monétaire est mise en œuvre, puis explique pourquoi conserver d'importants bilans n'a pas permis d'obtenir les avantages mis en avant. J'esquisse enfin une approche visant à alléger les bilans des banques centrales sans déstabiliser les marchés financiers.

JEL : E52, E58

Mots-clés : achats d'actifs, banque centrale, dénouement, politique monétaire, stabilité financière

The balance sheets of most central have ballooned following their asset purchases in the wake of the Great Financial Crisis (GFC) and of the pandemic crisis. This ballooning occurred as the policy rate had reached levels at which central banks considered it could not be lowered anymore, and central banks still wished to make monetary policy more accommodating. They thus chose to compress term premia on maturities beyond those traded in the money markets by buying bonds, conducting large-scale asset purchases (LSAPs, also called “Quantitative Easing” – QE – in the media). LSAPs in turn implied larger balance sheets. However, reversing this sort of monetary policy easing, i.e. “unwinding”, was not prioritised when inflationary pressures resurfaced. Instead, central banks first raised interest rates and kept large balance sheets, making this feature part of a “New Normal” (Pfister and Sahuc, 2020). Currently, central banks' portfolios have dwindled from their peaks, in particular in the euro area and in the United States, on which this paper focuses. However, no major central bank, and specifically neither the Federal Reserve (FED), nor the European Central Bank (ECB), has announced an objective to “unwind”ⁱⁱ. I first briefly remind some basics of monetary policy implementation, then explain the reasons for unwinding and finally outline an approach to do it.

1. Monetary policy implementation

I first present some general considerations, then illustrate them with the cases of the ECB and the FED.

General considerations

Monetary policy is implemented by creating and destroying reserves (i.e., deposits of the banks with the central bank). The sum of reserves is referred to as “banking liquidity”, or more simply

“liquidity”. Banks can recycle reserves in the interbank market. Reserves are created by the central bank buying assets (essentially, foreign currency and securities) and by lending to banks against collateral, labelled “refinancing”. They are destroyed when the assets held by the central bank are redeemed or sold, or when the loans to the banks mature. The demand for reserves can be reinforced by a reserve requirement system, with interest paid on required reserves to avoid financial repression and averaging of required reserves over a maintenance period to help smooth the demand for reserves and thus interbank market rates.

A central bank’s simplified balance sheet helps illustrate these mechanisms, keeping in mind that a balance sheet is always balanced (i.e. assets equal liabilities).

Simplified central bank’s balance sheet

Assets	Liabilities
1. Refinancing	6. Reserves (inc. required reserves, excess reserves and deposit facility)
2. Monetary policy portfolio	7. Liquidity-withdrawing open market operations (inc. reverse repos)
3. Foreign exchange reserves (inc. gold)	8. Banknotes
4. Capital assets	9. Treasury account
5. Other assets	10. Other liabilities
	11. Own funds

One can neglect items 3, because the central bank usually does not intervene in the foreign exchange or gold markets, as well as items 4, 5, 9, 10 and 11, because they are negligible and/or shocks on them are easily neutralised (“sterilised” in the jargon of central bankers) through open market operations (items 1 and 7), so that they do not influence the volume of reserves. Consequently, there are two possibilities:

- Either the volume of banknotes (item 8) is higher or close to that of monetary policy operations (items 1 + 2 - 7), and then reserves (item 6) are scarce. In the terms of Borio (2023), this is a scarce reserves system (SRS). In an SRS, the central bank can operate an interest rate corridor, aiming to stabilize the overnight rate in the middle of the corridor, at which it either provides liquidity through regular refinancing operations (item 1) or withdraws liquidity through regular liquidity-withdrawing operations (item 7) (Bindseil, 2004). So, items 1 and 7 in principle do not coexist. So as to exert a minimal influence on the markets of the underlying assets, these operations are conducted in the repurchase markets. In these markets, central banks intervene in the same way as a private agent. Accordingly, these operations are referred to as open market operations. The lower limit of the corridor (the “floor”) is set by the deposit facility rate – DFR – and the higher limit (the “ceiling”) by that on the Lombard facility (the marginal lending rate – MLR – for the ECB and the discount facility for the FED). The Lombard facility is intended to serve both as a lending of last resort for the banking sector as a whole, in case of a financial crisis, and as a penalty rate for individual banks which have mismanaged their liquidity and would otherwise end the day with an overdraft at the central bank, which is not allowed. The central bank can also conduct (liquidity-providing or withdrawing) fine-tuning operations, in particular at the end of the required

reserves maintenance period, when required reserves lose their interest-rate smoothing property (Bindseil, 2004).

- Or the volume of banknotes is significantly lower than that of monetary policy operations, and reserves are abundant, with the central bank operating an ample reserve system (ARS), according to Borio (2023)ⁱⁱⁱ. In an ARS, refinancing (item 1) is in principle useless, since banks which need it can easily find liquidity in the interbank market. Furthermore, the central bank is unable to collect all the excess liquidity in the repo market (item 7), where it would crowd out private participants. It thus collects deposits (item 6) through its deposit facility or simply pays interest on excess reserves (i.e., reserves held beyond the volume of required reserves), thus in principle putting a floor on very short-term interbank rates. The central bank then operates a floor system.

By unwinding, the central bank moves back from an ARS to an SRS^{iv}.

The cases of the ECB and the FED

Both central banks have been operating a floor system, in an ARS context, since 2008 for the FED, and 2009 for the ECB and do not intend to change this in the foreseeable future.

The ECB

Even though it was operating a floor system, the ECB has continued to conduct regular refinancing operations (so-called “main refinancing operations” - MROs), referring to the interest rate on these operations as the policy rate. However, it is the deposit facility rate that has played that role since 2009, with the overnight rate close to it (for more details on the evolutions of the ECB’s monetary policy operational framework in the wake of the GFC, see Eser et al., 2012). It has also maintained a corridor, the width of which it narrowed from 100 basis points to 50 basis points. Above all, it has been providing liquidity at fixed rate with full allotment at its MROs since October 2008 (i.e., provided they hold the required collateral, counterparties get all the liquidity they bid for at the ECB pre-announced rate). It thereby de facto put a ceiling on interbank rates at the MRO rate, at least at the maturity of these operations (one week). Although the marginal lending facility was maintained, the MLR thus ceased to act as a ceiling to money market rates (Pfister and Sahuc, 2020). Furthermore, the ECB continued to provide liquidity at maturities of up to three years through its longer-term refinancing operations (LTROs), also according to a fixed rate full allotment procedure since May 2010. It thus began to directly influence interest rates at the corresponding maturities, instead of acting indirectly through MROs’ rate expectations, as it did before.

In March 2024, the ECB Governing Council issued a statement on changes to the operational framework for implementing monetary policy (ECB, 2024), announcing it introduced only marginal adjustments with:

- The deposit facility “continuing to be” the instrument to steer monetary policy.
- The spread between the rate on MROs and DFR reduced to 15 basis points as from 18 September 2024, “in order to incentivise bidding in the weekly operations”.
- The other features of its operational framework unchanged. In particular, the ECB was very vague about a possible unwinding, stating that “New structural longer-term refinancing operations and a structural portfolio of securities will be introduced at a later stage, once the Eurosystem balance sheet begins to grow durably again, taking into account legacy bond holdings”. The ECB did not explain what such structural longer-

term refinancing or structural portfolio of securities consisted in, why they would be needed or on the basis of which criteria it would consider the Eurosystem portfolio would “grow durably again”. However, the reference to a “structural” and thus permanent securities portfolio, as well as to the use of the deposit facility to steer monetary policy, can be interpreted as signalling that the ECB does not envisage to unwind.

The FED

Before the GFC, the FED could put a ceiling on money market short-term rates with its discount facility. However, it tightly controlled the federal funds (fed funds) rate, which is an overnight rate on which it announced a target, through very frequent open market operations, thus preventing it from hitting the ceiling. Thus, in spite of operating within an SRS, the FED did not, properly speaking, have a corridor, unless one considers the fed funds rate as an implicit floor and ceiling.

The FED started operating a floor system when it was authorised by Congress, from October 2008 onwards, to pay interest on reserves, the interest on reserves balances (IORB). However, it maintained a target on the fed funds rate. Furthermore, in view of the role played in the financing of the economy by non-bank financial institutions (NBFIs), which do not have access to reserve balances or cannot receive IORB, the FED introduced an Overnight Reverse Repo facility (ON RRP) in December 2015. This facility is available to a wide range of money market lenders, including banks which are also present in the fed funds market, and acts as the floor to the effective fed funds rate (EFRR) (Afonso et al., 2022), which thus remains tightly controlled. On January 2019, the Federal Open Market Committee (FOMC) announced that it intended to continue to implement monetary policy in a regime of ample supply of reserves. It thus did not use the phrase “abundant reserves”, but also signalled it has no project to return to an STS.

Overall, both the ECB and the Fed seem to have piled an ARS over an SRS, as if a period of permanent financial crisis had been entered.

2. Why unwind

Not only did the expected benefits of an ARS not materialise, but ARSs have costs.

Expected benefits

An ARS can be expected to bring benefits in implementing both monetary policy and financial stability policies (see, e.g., Board of Governors, 2019, Borio, 2023, Hauser, 2023, Schnabel, 2023).

Monetary policy

In comparison with an SRS, an ARS can be expected to present three main advantages:

- An ARS is simpler to communicate, since there is in principle only one policy rate, the rate on reserves.
- It is also simpler to operate, as the central bank can rely on the high level of excess reserves to absorb shocks in so-called “autonomous factors” (i.e., items 3 to 5 and 8 to 11), which influence the level of liquidity and are not within the direct influence of the central bank. Open market operations can thus be dispensed with, as well as accurate liquidity forecasts. Conversely, both are needed in an SRS, since small errors in the

supply of reserves can then have a large impact on their price. In the words of the FOMC, in an ARS, “active management of the supply of reserves is not required” (Board of Governors, 2019) and the central bank would thus be able to implement monetary policy in an essentially passive manner.

- It is at least as efficient as an SRS to control the level and the volatility of the overnight rate. In fact, one would expect the overnight rate to hover very slightly above the rate on reserves, with the spread between the two rates reflecting the absence of credit risk on the central bank, as opposed to commercial banks.

However, as seen above in the cases of the ECB and the FED, central banks have maintained open market operations, which makes operational frameworks less readable. Furthermore, in contrast with the essence of an ARS, open market operations have repeatedly been used not just to withdraw but also to provide liquidity, and routinely so in the case of the ECB since MROs and LTROs are conducted according to a fixed calendar. Finally, the rate on reserves did not act as a floor to the overnight rate, with instead the former lying most of the time below it, in the euro area as well as in the U.S., since an ARS has been in place. This reflects the arbitrage between reserves and other monetary assets, in particular short-term Treasury securities (Martin et al., 2020). The latter have the advantage of being accessible to a much wider range of investors than reserves, which are accessible only to banks, while being as safe, and thus usually pay a lower interest rate. As the spread between short-term Treasury securities and the interest on reserves varies, an ARS introduces a speculative motive in the demand for reserves, as noted by Borio (2023). This makes the demand for reserves extremely variable, possibly justifying the conduct of open market operations, in contrast to the simplicity an ARS is supposed to foster.

Financial stability

An ARS could contribute to financial stability in three ways:

- In an ARS, the central bank, by providing excess liquidity in advance, would limit the risk of having to play the role of lender of last resort (LoLR) in case of financial stress. However, in the past few years, central banks have repeatedly intervened to provide liquidity during periods of stress in money markets. Examples were in September 2019, when dollar repo markets were under stress, in March 2022 during the global “Dash for Cash” episode, or in March 2023 when the Silicon Valley Bank collapsed.
- An ARS would help banks fulfil their liquidity requirements, in particular the Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR)^v. Indeed, banks can fulfil the LCR requirement partly or fully by holding reserves if they wish. However, accepting this amounts to transferring the onus of complying with the prudential requirement from banks to central banks, and to transforming a prudential requirement into a constraint on monetary policy.
- Finally, an ARS could also help make up a shortage of safe assets (Caballero et al., 2017). However, the reserves added to create an ARS have been provided when central banks purchased Treasury securities, which are themselves safe assets. It is thus not clear that an ARS adds to the preexisting stock of safe assets. Furthermore, in order to fulfil the liquidity requirements, banks can create the high-quality liquid assets (HQLA) they need through securitisation (Pfister and Sahuc, 2020).

Costs

ARSs have five sorts of costs:

- They create risks of losses for central banks. These risks have materialized in the recent years as interest rates were raised and interest payments on deposits with the central bank became higher than those collected on the bonds they had purchased. For instance, the ECB recorded a loss of close to €8bn in both 2023 and 2024. Although profit is not an objective of central banks, an extended period of losses could jeopardize their independence and be detrimental to their reputation as frugal institutions.
- ARSs can also be at the source of market malfunctioning, in particular in the money market. Borio (2023) notes that transactions in the dollar and the euro interbank markets have fallen dramatically with the increase in the supply of reserves. Schnabel (2024) also points that euro repurchase markets were strained “at some point”, as collateral, which was mobilised by ECB operations, was scarce.
- ARSs give rise to price distortions, as the stock of securities purchased by the central bank and its renewal as the securities mature put pressure on term premia. According to the ECB, the impact of current and expected Eurosystem bond holdings lowered ten-year sovereign bond yields by around 175 basis points when at its peak in early 2022 and still by 75 points in January 2025 (Cipollone, 2025). These price distortions were created deliberately when risks of deflation were perceived and central banks considered an effective lower bound (ELB) for interest rates had been reached. However, maintaining them permanently does not seem justified.
- They create moral hazard. To the extent that banks are assured that they will have at their disposal the liquidity they require, including at medium-term maturities in the euro area, they are disincentivised from implementing a prudent liquidity management. This is in contrast with the spirit of prudential regulation, particularly in the case when liquidity is not provided at a penalty rate or even a market rate, but instead at a fixed rate with full allotment as is the case in the ECB’s MROs and LTROs. In that regard, it is notable that Tony Gravelle, Deputy Governor of the Bank of Canada, states that one reason for returning to the pre-QE monetary policy is market discipline (Gravelle, 2025)^{vi}.
- They blunt the monetary policy transmission mechanism. Banks, which are awash with cash, are not incentivised to collect more deposits when interest rates are raised. Byrne and Foster (2024) find that pass-through in the recent ECB tightening cycle was weaker relative to previous cycles for household deposits. The lack of appetite of banks for the collection of deposits may also explain why the FED found it necessary to create the ON RRP to facilitate the transmission of monetary policy impulses to NBFIs. Reserves also substitute partly for loans in the balance sheets of banks: Diamond et al. (2023) show, using a structural model for the U.S., that reserves injected by LSAPs raised loan rates by 8.2 basis points, and each dollar of reserves reduced bank lending by 8.1 cents^{vii}.

3. How unwind

Unwinding would not necessarily be without difficulties. I first explain how the costs of an ARS could be eliminated in the transition process to an SRS, then outline a possible approach.

Eliminating the costs of an ARS

Some costs can hardly be eliminated. For instance, if central banks raise interest rates and, as a consequence pay interest on the reserves which are higher than those they collect on the bonds they hold, they would have to make huge profits on other assets to offset the corresponding losses.

Other costs would be eliminated quasi automatically as unwinding proceeds. This should be the case of market malfunctioning, as transactions in the interbank market should develop as reserves become less ample and also in the repurchase market as holdings of bonds by the central bank are run down. The latter factor would also contribute to a normalisation in the bond markets where the central bank's footprint would be reduced. This normalisation would take place all the more rapidly that the unwinding and the intended schedule would be announced publicly (see below). Finally, the rundown of reserves should strengthen competition between banks to collect deposits and leave more room in their balance sheets to distribute credit, thus sharpening the monetary transmission mechanism.

A cost which can be eliminated, or at least reduced, and will not necessarily be when unwinding is moral hazard. In particular if, as the ECB, the central bank insists that the supply of reserves is demand-driven, as is the case with full allotment, and does not wish banks to have recourse to emergency (i.e. Lombard) refinancing at a penalty rate, moral hazard will persist. Some guiding principles that could be useful to eliminate or at least significantly reduce moral hazard could be:

- Dissociating monetary policy and financial stability policies, with corresponding instruments, in the spirit of the 'Tinbergen rule' (Pfister and Valla, 2018). In particular, the creation and destruction of reserves, which is at the heart of monetary policy implementation, should be used for this sole purpose, with the intervention of the central bank as a LoLR being part of monetary policy in times of financial crises. Furthermore, the central bank should use monetary policy instruments for signalling its monetary policy, not for protecting banks against the consequences of imprudent management. Consequently, as noted by Pfister and Sahuc (2020), central banks could tolerate more interest rate volatility or even discontinue the practice of targeting a market interest rate (in that regard, officially, the ECB does not have an operational target and thus does not officially target the interbank overnight rate).
- In line with the latter dissociation, a clear assignment of responsibilities, meaning it is for the central bank to conduct monetary policy and it is for banks to comply with prudential requirements. This implies that banks have to find their own ways to fulfil these requirements and that the central bank can only intervene as an LoLR, thus through its Lombard facility at a penalty rate. In that regard, the so-called 'stigma effect' (i.e., banks shying away from having recourse to the Lombard facility because this would hurt their reputation if it were known) should not be overplayed. On the side of banks, having such recourse is certainly better than defaulting. On the side of the central bank, it has an obligation of discretion and the names of the banks that have recourse to the discount facility do not have to be disclosed (the FED has even an obligation to disclose them only two years after it has granted discount window refinancing).

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A possible approach

Unwinding should avoid destabilising financial markets. With this objective in mind, I first describe general orientations, then the main steps of a possible path toward an SRS.

General orientations

To avoid destabilizing financial markets, unwinding should proceed in a credible and transparent manner. This presupposes that:

- The objective (restoring an SRS, conducive to a better functioning of financial markets) would be announced in advance of implementation.
- Before or at the same time as the announcement of the objective, the breakdown, by ranges of maturities and categories of issuers, of the portfolio of bonds held by the central bank would be made public (this has been the case for the FED since it started conducting LSAPs, but is still not the case for the ECB).
- A tentative timeline, with caveats in case of unforeseen economic and financial developments, would also be announced, preferably at the same time as the objective;
- The main steps of unwinding would also be described in the communiqué announcing the objective.

The main steps

In order not to destabilize bond markets, the reference scenario could be the one in which the central bank holds the bonds in its portfolio, without rolling it, until they are redeemed. The restoration of an SRS may thus be a lengthy process. Caveats could also state that, in case of financial crisis and the reaching of the ELB, LSAPs could resume, or alternatively, in case of high economic growth threatening price stability, bonds could be sold in the markets, while taking care not to destabilise them. In that regard, the precedent of the so-called “taper tantrum” in May 2013 should not obscure the fact when, two weeks earlier, Ben Bernanke had announced to Congress the intention of the FED to unwind, possibly by selling bonds in the markets, the latter had not reacted. Furthermore, in the scenario I refer to, bond markets would be told about this possibility much more in advance.

The possible main steps could be, in chronological order:

- A discontinuation of open market liquidity-providing operations, which both seem unnecessary and hamper the functioning of the interbank market by substituting for market transactions. This would in particular be the case for the ECB’s MROs and LTROs^{viii}.
- A widening of the interest rate corridor, in order to encourage banks both to resume transactions in the interbank market and to securitize, thus taking care of their liquidity position. Indeed, as money market very short rates increase toward the middle of the interest rate corridor, surpassing the rate on reserves, holding reserves to fulfil the LCR would become more costly for banks. This widening should take place progressively, until the corridor reaches the pre-GFC level (100 basis points)^{ix}.
- A restoration of open market liquidity-providing operations, when market interest rates move on a sustained basis close to that of the Lombard facility, and thus possibly before the interest rate corridor reaches its pre-GFC level.

- Finally, although this is not tightly related to the restoration of an SRS, and if needed to strengthen the transmission mechanism of monetary policy, as the Fed wished (see above), a widening of access to central bank deposits to NBFIs. From a legal point of view, this could be easily feasible for the ECB^x, but more difficult for the FED, as the permission of Congress would be required. Access to central bank deposit accounts, which would help NBFIs get better remuneration on their assets as a result of an improvement of their bargaining position vis-à-vis banks, should not necessarily go hand-in-hand with access to refinancing from the central bank. This would be for two reasons: the first one is that NBFIs, which do not collect deposits from the public, are less subject to runs than banks, the second reason is to lessen moral hazard, as NBFIs may become less prudent if they have access to central bank refinancing.

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ⁱⁱ One exception is the Bank of Canada, whose Deputy Governor Toni Gravelle has announced it would have unwound, although he does not use the word, and returned to the pre-QE monetary policy framework in the course of third quarter of 2025 (Gravelle, 2025). However, this monetary policy framework is quite specific, since the Bank of Canada, which does not aim at keeping commercial banks "in the Bank", does not have reserve requirements and does not conduct refinancing operations at preset regular intervals. Instead, in normal times, it

targets settlement balances, which are needed in rather small volumes, by conducting daily fine tuning operations in both directions, either lending or borrowing in the market for reserves.

ⁱⁱⁱ The distinction between SRS and ARS is more general than that used by central banks, between a structural liquidity deficit and a structural liquidity surplus, implying respectively that the central bank systematically lends or borrows in the interbank market and thus ignoring the situation in which it lends occasionally, which is included in an SRS.

^{iv} The central bank can also restore an SRS by issuing bonds, if it has this capacity (this is the case of the ECB, but not of the FED). However, this means it would not unwind and is thus out of the scope of this paper.

^v The LCR requires that banks have an adequate stock of unencumbered high-quality liquid assets (HQLAs), i.e., assets which can be converted easily and immediately in private markets into cash to meet their liquidity needs, for a 30-calendar day liquidity stress scenario.

^{vi} Gravelle goes on explaining “What do I mean by this? Well, we don’t want to see major banks and other core financial institutions under-investing in their capacity to robustly manage their liquidity because they have developed an unhealthy over-reliance on settlement balances. In managing their liquidity needs, financial market participants should be able to respond to fluctuations in those needs in other ways—for example, through access to markets” (Gravelle, 2025, page 7).

^{vii} Some of these costs (risks of losses, price distortions, banks’ balance sheets encumbrance) would be kept in case the central bank would issue bonds to restore an SRS (see endnote IV).

^{viii} This suggestion raises the issue of why the ECB has maintained these operations. One possible explanation could be that the ECB’s decision reflects political economy considerations, rather than analytical motives. For instance, some ten years after it has taken over the supervision of banks in the euro area, the ECB might wish to avoid that some banks, which still have difficulties to access to the interbank market, default. It would thus extend them a lifeline. Another possibility, complementary to the previous one, could be that the ECB has maintained MROs and LTROs in order to be able to refinance banks in euro area countries under public finance stress which would buy sovereign bonds. This way, MROs and LTROs would allow to protect sovereigns, less visibly and more flexibly than using the Transmission Protection Instrument (ECB, 2022).

^{ix} One possibility, suggested by Pfister and Valla (2018), could also be to keep a narrow corridor and create a new facility putting a ceiling to very short-term interbank rates, accessible only to banks posting investment grade collateral, while a broad range of collateral could still be accepted at the Lombard facility, the exclusive role of which would to act as an LoLR facility. This would allow the central bank to better limit interest rate volatility in the money markets.

^x Art. 17 of the Statutes of the European System of Central Banks and the European Central Bank states that: “In order to conduct their operations, the ECB and the national central banks may open accounts for credit institutions, public entities and other market participants”. The ECB has granted access to central bank accounts to non-bank payment service providers on 27 January 2025.